

Syntheses, spectral and antimicrobial studies of the coordination compounds of the Schiff base containing aliphatic hydrazone moiety

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Manuscript received online 18 February 2013, revised 07 April 2013, accepted 29 April 2013

Abstract : Salicylaldehyde and 3-oxobutanehydrazide react in equimolar ratio in EtOH and form the Schiff base, *N*-(2-hydroxybenzal)-3-oxobutanehydrazone, LH₃ (**1**). The latter reacts with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions in 2 : 1 molar ratio and forms the coordination compounds, [M(LH₂)₂] (**2**; M = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd), [Zr(OH)₂(LH₂)₂] (**3**) and [MoO₂(LH₂)₂] (**4**) respectively. The coordination compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, spectral (IR, reflectance, ¹H NMR, ESR) and magnetic susceptibility measurements. **1** acts as a monobasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in 2-4 coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms. **2** (M = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu) is paramagnetic, while remaining compounds, **2** (where M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** are diamagnetic. The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of **1-4** were carried out through agar well diffusion method. They are active against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus* MTCC 96 and *B. subtilis* MTCC 121), Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* MTCC 1652 and *P. aeruginosa* MTCC 741) and yeast (*C. albicans* MTCC 3017 and *S. cerevisiae* MTCC 170). Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd attain a coordination number of 6, while Zr and Mo attain a coordination number of 8 in their respective compounds.

Keywords : Antimicrobial studies, coordination compounds, magnetic studies, Schiff base, spectral studies.

Introduction

The pharmaceutical (antitumour, antiviral, antituberculosis, antimicrobial and enzymatic) and industrial (analytical reagents, polymer coatings, fluorescent materials etc.) importance of the coordination compounds of the Schiff bases containing the hydrazone moiety are well known¹⁻³. A perusal of the literature indicates that much work has been reported on the Schiff bases containing the salicylaldehyde moiety alone⁴ or hydrazide alone⁵, however there is no report on the coordination compounds of the Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 3-oxobutanehydrazide. Keeping in view, the above importance of the compounds possessing the hydrazone moiety, we thought it worthwhile to synthesize and characterize the coordination compounds of the Schiff base, LH₃ (**1**) with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions. The Schiff base (**1**) and its coordination compounds (**2-4**) are active against Gram-positive

bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria and yeast.

Results and discussion

The nucleophilic addition reaction between salicylaldehyde and 3-oxobutanehydrazide in equimolar ratio in EtOH followed by the elimination of one water molecule results in the formation of the Schiff base, *N*-(2-hydroxybenzal)-3-oxobutanehydrazone, LH₃ (**1**) (Scheme 1).

A MeOH solution of **1** reacts with a MeOH solution of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions in 2 : 1 molar ratio and forms the corresponding compounds, **2-4** (Scheme 2).

The coordination compounds are insoluble in H₂O, MeOH and EtOH but fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. They are air-stable up to 190 °C and get decomposed above this temperature. The molecular weight measurements in diphenyl indicate their monomeric nature⁶. Their molar conductance data⁷ (4.9–8.9 mho cm² mol⁻¹ in DMSO) reveal their non-electrolytic nature (Table 1).

Infrared spectral studies :

The IR spectra of **1-4** were recorded in KBr and the prominent absorption bands are given in Table 2. **1** exhibits the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ (intramolecular H-bond), $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine), $\nu(\text{C-O})\Phi$ and $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (enolic) stretches at 3212, 1598, 1503 and 1242 cm⁻¹ respectively. The $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) stretch of **1** shifts to lower energy by 9–34 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination through its azomethine N atom⁸. The $\nu(\text{C-O})\Phi$ stretch of **1** shifts to higher energy by ≤ 10 cm⁻¹ supporting the involve-

ment of phenolic O atom towards coordination⁹. The magnitude of the above shift of the $\nu(\text{C-O})\Phi$ stretch indicates a monomeric structure for **2-4**. The $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (enolic) stretch of **1** occurring at 1242 cm⁻¹ shifts by 14–50 cm⁻¹ in **2-4**¹⁰. Therefore, the Schiff base behaves as a monobasic tridentate ONO donor ligand coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms. The involvement of phenolic/enolic O and azomethine N atoms towards coordination is further supported by the appearance of new non-ligand bands between 600–625 and 460–500 cm⁻¹ due to the $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ vibrations in **2-4**. These bands are in the expected order of increasing energy : $\nu(\text{M-N}) < \nu(\text{M-O})$ ¹¹ as expected due to the greater dipole moment change in the M–O vibration, greater electronegativity of the O atom than N atom and shorter M–O bond length than the M–N bond length¹². The $\nu_s(\text{O=Mo=O})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretches occur at 970 and 895 cm⁻¹ respectively in **4** and these bands occur in the usual range (892–964 cm⁻¹; 840–925 cm⁻¹) reported for the majority of MoO₂^{VI} compounds¹³. The IR data are indicative of the presence of a *cis*-MoO₂ moiety in the present case, as a compound possessing *trans*-MoO₂ moiety is expected to show only the $\nu_{as}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch, since the $\nu_s(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch is IR inactive¹⁴. The absence of a band at ~ 770 cm⁻¹ in the present MoO₂^{VI} coordination compound indicates the absence of an oligomeric structure with $\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots$ inter-

Scheme 1

2; M = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd

3

4

Scheme 2

action¹³. The absence of a band between 835–955 cm^{-1} , characteristic of $\nu(\text{Zr}=\text{O})$ stretch¹⁵ in **3** suggests its structure as $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH}_2)_2]$ and not as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{LH}_2)_2]$. The appearance of a band at 1140 cm^{-1} due to the $\delta(\text{Zr}-\text{OH})$ bending mode also supports the suggested structure of the compound¹⁶.

Reflectance spectral studies :

The coordination compound, **2** (M = Mn) shows three bands at 16220, 21310 and 25850 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)(\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, in an octahedral environment¹⁷. The coordination compound, **2** (M = Co) shows three bands at 9200, 13500 and 19750 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, in an octahedral environment¹⁸. Using the value of free ion Racah parameter ($B = 971 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), the calculated values of $\nu_3 : \nu_1$, $10Dq$, B , β , B° and CFSE are 2.14, 10360 cm^{-1} , 780.69, 0.80, 20% and $-99.23 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively^{18,19}. The coordination compound, **2** (M = Ni) exhibits three bands at 9000, 16350 and 25550 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ions¹⁸. Using the value of free ion Racah parameter ($B = 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)²⁰, the calculated values of $\nu_2 : \nu_1$, $10Dq$, B , β , B° and CFSE are 1.82, 9000 cm^{-1} , 890.92, 0.86, 14% and $-129.30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively^{18,19}. The reduction of Racah parameter (from the free ion values : 971 cm^{-1} to 780.69 cm^{-1} for Co^{II} and from 1030 cm^{-1} to 890.92 cm^{-1} for Ni^{II}) and the values of % covalence in **2** (20%, when M = Co^{II} and 14%, when M = Ni^{II}) are indicative of the covalent nature of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} compounds. The value of $10Dq$ of the Co^{II} compound (10360 cm^{-1}) is greater than that of the corresponding Ni^{II} compound (9000 cm^{-1}). This is in line with the spectrochemical series of metal ions for a given ligand, given stoichiometry and a given stereochemistry²¹ : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$. The higher negative CFSE value of the Ni^{II} compound in comparison to that of the corresponding Co^{II} compound is as expected. The compound, **2** (M = Cu) shows one broad peak at 22580 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition indicating distorted octahedral geometry²².

ESR spectral studies :

The ESR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH}_2)_2]$ (**2**; M = Cu) in DMSO at liquid nitrogen temperature has been recorded in X-band, using 100 kHz field modulation and the g values (Table 3) are relative to the standard marker, tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) ($g = 2.0023$). The observed values of g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} , α^2_{Cu} , $(\alpha')^2$ and G are

2.28, 2.11, 2.17, $1.682 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $3.74 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 0.83, 0.23 and 2.57 respectively. From the observed values of various parameters, it is concluded that the ground state of Cu^{II} is $d_{x^2-y^2}$ (2B_1 as the ground state) and the compound possesses an octahedral structure²³. There is a significant covalent character in the Cu-L bond²⁴.

NMR studies :

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of **1**, **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** were recorded in DMSO- d_6 . The chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm downfield from TMS²⁵. **1** exhibits a

singlet at δ 2.38 ppm due to the methyl protons, a singlet at δ 2.9 ppm due to the methine proton, a multiplet between δ 6.2–7.44 ppm due to the aromatic protons, a singlet at δ 7.91 ppm due to the azomethine proton, a broad signal at δ 8.72 ppm due to the phenolic proton and a singlet at δ 10.23 ppm due to the enolic O-H proton. The absence of the resonance signals due to the phenolic proton in **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** indicates the deprotonation of their OH groups followed by involvement in coordination. The signal due to the azomethine

Table 1. Analytical, colour, molar conductance ($\text{mho cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and molecular weight data of compounds

Sl. No.	Compound	Stoichiometry	Colour	Λ_M ($\text{mho cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	M. Wt.	Found (Calcd.) (%)			
						M	C	H	N
1.	1	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	Yellow	–	220 ^a (220)	–	60.06 (60.00)	5.55 (5.45)	12.87 (12.73)
2.	2 (M=Mn)	$\text{MnC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Chocolate	8.9	493.2 ^a (492.9)	11.23 (11.14)	53.47 (53.56)	4.54 (4.46)	11.29 (11.36)
3.	2 (M=Co)	$\text{CoC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Blue	4.9	479.0 ^b (496.9)	12.00 (11.85)	53.62 (53.13)	4.63 (4.43)	11.46 (11.27)
4.	2 (M=Ni)	$\text{NiC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Green	6.8	480.2 ^b (496.7)	11.57 (11.82)	52.96 (53.15)	4.32 (4.43)	11.48 (11.27)
5.	2 (M=Cu)	$\text{CuC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Brown	5.3	494.8 ^b (501.5)	12.64 (12.66)	52.67 (52.64)	4.32 (4.39)	11.16 (11.16)
6.	2 (M=Zn)	$\text{ZnC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Cream	6.2	498.5 ^b (503.4)	13.16 (12.99)	52.47 (52.44)	4.46 (4.37)	11.09 (11.12)
7.	2 (M=Cd)	$\text{CdC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Off white	7.5	533.4 ^b (550.4)	21.36 (20.42)	47.69 (47.96)	4.09 (4.00)	10.24 (10.17)
8.	3	$\text{ZrC}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_8$	Yellow	7.0	574.7 ^b (563.2)	17.14 (16.19)	46.84 (46.87)	4.18 (4.26)	9.93 (9.94)
9.	4	$\text{MoC}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_8$	Pale-yellow	6.4	545.9 ^b (565.9)	17.17 (16.95)	46.22 (46.65)	3.77 (3.89)	9.62 (9.90)

Abbreviations : ^aMass spectral data and ^bRast method data.

Table 2. IR, reflectance spectral data (cm^{-1}) and magnetic moments of the coordination compounds

Sl. No.	Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine)	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\Phi$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (enolic)	ν_{max}	Mag. moment (B.M.)
1.	1	1598	1503	1242	–	–
2.	2 (M=Mn)	1580	1510	1277	16220, 21310, 25850	5.81
3.	2 (M=Co)	1577	1508	1260	9200, 13500, 19750	4.68
4.	2 (M=Ni)	1583	1510	1276	9000, 16350, 25550	3.42
5.	2 (M=Cu)	1589	1506	1281	22580	1.89
6.	2 (M=Zn)	1571	1507	1256	–	Diamagnetic
7.	2 (M = Cd)	1564	1507	1276	–	Diamagnetic
8.	3	1588	1508	1292	–	Diamagnetic
9.	4	1580	1507	1272	–	Diamagnetic

proton appears at lower δ value in **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4**. This downward shift is indicative of coordination of N atom of >C=N- group²⁵.

Mass spectra :

The EIMS mass spectra of **1** and **2** (M = Mn) were recorded on Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micro-mass Spectrometer. The prominent fragmentation peaks in **1** observed at $m/z = 220, 219, 218, 205, 203, 188, 186, 163, 134, 126, 120$ and 106 are tentatively assigned to $[M]^+$, $[M-1H]^+$, $[M-2H]^+$, $[M-Me]^+$, $[M-OH]^+$, $[M-MeOH]^+$, $[M-2OH]^+$, $[M-MeCOHCH]^+$, $[M-MeCOHCHCOH]^+$, $[M-C_6H_5OH]^+$ and $[M-MeCOHCHCOHN]^+$ respectively. The prominent fragmentation peaks in **2** (M = Mn) observed at $m/z = 493, 492, 478, 461, 436, 410, 407, 379, 360, 274, 219, 133$ and 114 are tentatively assigned to $[M]^+$, $[M-1H]^+$, $[M-Me]^+$, $[M-MeOH]^+$, $[M-CHCMeOH]^+$, $[M-NCCHCMeOH]^+$, $[M-HOCMeCHCOH]^+$, $[M-HOCMeCHCOHN_2]^+$, $[M-C_6H_4OCHN_2]^+$, $[M-LH_2]^+$, $[M-MnLH_2]^+$, $[M-MnC_{15}H_{17}N_2O_5]^+$ and $[M-MnC_{18}H_{16}N_2O_4]^+$ respectively. The peaks at $m/z = 493, 274$ and 219 further support the proposed 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the present compound, the loss of one molecule of the Schiff base and the loss of one molecule of the Schiff base plus manganese metal respectively.

Magnetic measurements :

The room temperature magnetic moment of **2** (M = Mn) is 5.81 B.M., which lies in the normal range re-

ported for the magnetically dilute octahedral compounds of Mn^{II} ions²⁶. The magnetic moment of **2** (M = Co) is 4.68 B.M., which lies in the usual range reported for the octahedral Co^{II} compounds²⁷. The magnetic moment of **2** (M = Ni) is 3.42 B.M. indicating octahedral geometry around the Ni^{II} ion^{26,27}. The magnetic moment of **2** (M = Cu) is 1.89 B.M. indicating octahedral geometry around the Cu^{II} ion²⁸. This value lies within the range (1.70–2.20 B.M.) reported for the magnetically dilute Cu^{II} compounds²⁸. The coordination compounds, **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** are diamagnetic.

Antimicrobial studies :

The newly synthesized compounds (**1-4**) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against two Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*) (32–256 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), one Gram-negative bacterium (*E. coli*) (128 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and two fungi (*C. albicans*, *S. cerevisiae*) (16–256 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) respectively (Tables 3 and 4). The activities of the compounds were evaluated by measuring the inhibition zone observed around the tested compounds. Positive controls produced significantly sized inhibition zones against the above bacteria and fungi, however, negative control produced no observable inhibitory effect against any of the test organisms. The results indicate that all the coordination compounds have higher activity than the Schiff base. The compound, **4** was the most effective against Gram-positive bacteria with zone of inhibition of 19.6 mm and 22.3 mm respectively. The compound, **2**

Table 3. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of compounds through agar well diffusion method

Sl. No.	Compd.	Diameter of growth of inhibition zone (mm) ^a					
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1.	1	13.6	15.6	*	*	*	*
2.	2 (M=Mn)	15.6	16.3	15.6	*	16.3	14.6
3.	2 (M=Co)	14.3	15.3	*	*	18.3	15.3
4.	2 (M=Ni)	15.6	15.6	*	*	15.6	13.6
5.	2 (M=Cu)	16.3	19.3	16.3	*	14.3	15.3
6.	2 (M=Zn)	18.3	20.3	*	*	21.6	18.3
7.	2 (M=Cd)	17.6	21.6	*	*	20.6	15.6
8.	3	17.6	21.6	*	*	13.6	14.6
9.	4	19.6	22.3	*	*	16.3	15.3
10.	Ciprofloxacin	26.6	24.0	25.0	22.0	*	*
11.	Amphotericin-B	*	*	*	*	19.3	16.6

Abbreviations : ^aValues, including diameter of the well (8 mm), are means of three replicates.

* = No activity.

Table 4. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) (in $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of compounds by using modified agar well diffusion method

Sl. No.	Compd.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1.	1	256	128	*	*	*
2.	2 (M=Mn)	128	128	128	64	128
3.	2 (M=Co)	256	128	*	32	64
4.	2 (M=Ni)	128	128	*	64	256
5.	2 (M=Cu)	128	64	128	128	128
6.	2 (M=Zn)	64	64	*	16	32
7.	2 (M=Cd)	128	32	*	32	64
8.	3	128	32	*	128	64
9.	4	64	32	*	64	64
10.	Ciprofloxacin	6.25	6.25	6.25	*	*
11.	Amphotericin-B	*	*	*	12.5	12.5

Abbreviations : * = No activity.

(where M = Mn, Cu) was the most effective against Gram-negative bacterium with zone of inhibition of 15.6 mm and 16.3 mm respectively. The compound, **2** (M = Zn) was the most effective against fungi with zone of inhibition of 21.6 mm and 18.3 mm respectively. The compounds, **2** (M = Zn) and **4** were found to be the best as they exhibited the lowest MIC of 64 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *S. aureus*. The compounds, **2** (M = Cd), **3** and **4** showed lowest MIC of 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *B. subtilis*. However, in case of yeast, the compound, **2** (M = Zn) was found to be the best as it exhibited the lowest MIC of 16 and 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *S. cerevisiae* and *C. albicans* respectively. It is, therefore, suggested that the present compounds may be used in the pharmaceutical industries, after testing their toxicities to human beings.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate, copper(II) acetate monohydrate, ethyl acetoacetate, methyl salicylate [Loba Chemie]; zinc(II) acetate dihydrate, cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate, hexadecaquaoctahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) chloride [BDH]; ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate [BDH]; hydrazine hydrate [Fisher Scientific]; DMSO, DMF, MeOH and EtOH [Ranbaxy] were of AR grade and used as received. Hexadecaquaoctahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) acetate and bis(acetylacetonato)dioxo-

molybdenum(VI) were synthesized according to the literature procedures²⁹. All the microbial cultures were procured from microbial type culture collection (MTCC), IMTECH, Chandigarh. The bacteria were sub-cultured on nutrient agar, whereas yeast on malt yeast agar.

Analytical and physical measurements :

The estimation of metal contents, spectral studies (IR, reflectance, ¹H NMR, ESR) and the magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by the methods reported earlier³⁰. The melting points of the compounds were determined on digital melting point apparatus Stuart SMP-40. The molar conductances of the coordination compounds in DMSO were carried out on Digital Conductivity Meter HPG-3001. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the compounds were determined on a FLASH EA 1112 CHNS (O) Analyzer. The IR spectra of **1-4** were recorded in KBr (4000–250 cm^{-1}) on a Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectrometer Model RZX (Perkin-Elmer). The electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi-330 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra of 3-oxobutanehydrazide, **1**, **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** were recorded on an Avance-II (Bruker) FT NMR Spectrometer at 400 MHz using DMSO as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. The mass spectra of **1** and **2** (M = Mn) were recorded on Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micromass Spectrometer. The ESR spectrum of **2** (M = Cu) was recorded at LNT in solid on a Varian E-112 ESR

Spectrometer with X-band microwave frequency (9.1 GHz) using tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) as a *g*-marker and monitoring the frequency with a frequency meter. The magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature by Lakeshore VSM 7410 instrument. Antimicrobial studies of **1-4** were performed by agar well diffusion method³¹.

Antibacterial activity :

The antimicrobial activities of ligand (**1**) and its coordination compounds (**2-4**) were evaluated by the agar well diffusion method. All the microbial cultures were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard, which is visually comparable to a microbial suspension of approximately 1.5×10^8 cfu/mL. 20 ml of agar medium was poured into each Petri plate and the plates were swabbed with 100 μ L inocula of the test microorganisms and kept for 15 min for adsorption. Using sterile cork borer of 8 mm diameter, wells were bored into the seeded agar plates and these were loaded with a 100 μ L volume with concentration of 2.0 mg/mL of each compound reconstituted in DMSO. All the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Antimicrobial activity of each compound was evaluated by measuring the zone of growth inhibition against the test organisms with zone reader (Hi Antibiotic zone scale). DMSO was used as a negative control, whereas ciprofloxacin was used as positive control for bacteria and amphotericin-B for yeast. This procedure was performed in three replicate plates for each organism.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the compounds :

MIC is the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial compound that inhibits the visible growth of a microorganism after overnight incubation. MIC of the various compounds against bacterial and yeast strains was tested through a modified agar well diffusion method³¹. In this method, a two fold serial dilution of each compound was prepared by first reconstituting the compound in DMSO followed by dilution in sterile distilled water to achieve a decreasing concentration range of 512 to 1 μ g/mL. A 100 μ L volume of each dilution was introduced into wells (in triplicate) in the agar plates already seeded with 100 μ L of standardized inoculum (10^6 cfu/mL) of the test microbial strain. All test plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 h and observed for the inhibition

zones. MIC, taken as the lowest concentration of the compound that completely inhibited the growth of the microbe, showed by a clear zone of inhibition, was recorded for each test organism.

Synthesis of 3-oxobutanehydrazide (KBHz) :

Hydrazine hydrate (5.0 g, 100 mmol) was added slowly with continuous stirring to an ice-cooled EtOH solution (20 mL) of ethyl acetoacetate (13.0 g, 100 mmol) during a period of 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 h. The white compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with and recrystallised from EtOH and dried *in vacuo*. M.p. = 188 °C, yield = 90%; anal. [C₄H₈N₂O₂; found (calcd.)% C = 41.24 (41.38), H = 6.94 (6.90), N = 24.06 (24.14); IR bands (cm⁻¹) : 3298 ν (OH)(intramolecular H-bond), 2899 ν (N-H)(intramolecular H-bond), 1677 ν (C=O)(keto), 1618 δ (NH₂) and 1041 ν (N-N)(hydrazide); ¹H NMR signals (δ ppm) : (3H, -CH₃, 1.27), (2H, -CH₂, 2.58), (2H, -NH₂, 5.26), (1H, -CONH, 7.84).

Synthesis of 1 :

Salicylaldehyde (12.2 g, 100 mmol) and 3-oxobutanehydrazide (11.6 g, 100 mmol) were refluxed in EtOH (50 mL) on a water bath for 1 h. The excess of solvent was evaporated and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The yellow compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from EtOH and then dried as mentioned above. M.p. = 210 °C, yield = 70%; anal. [C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₃; found (calcd.)% C = 60.06 (60.00), H = 5.55 (5.45), N = 12.87 (12.73); IR bands (cm⁻¹) : 3212 ν (OH)(intramolecular H-bond), 1598 ν (C=N)(azomethine), 1503 ν (C-O) Φ , 1242 ν (C-O)(enolic) and 1042 ν (N-N)(hydrazide); ¹H NMR signals (δ ppm) : (3H, -CH₃, 2.38), (1H, -CH, 2.9), (4H, -ArH, 6.2-7.44), (1H, -CH=N, 7.91), (1H, phenolic-OH, 8.72) and (2H, enolic-OH, 10.23).

Synthesis of 2-4 :

A MeOH solution (~30 mL) of appropriate metal acetate/compound (5 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (~100 mL) of **1** (1.1 g, 5 mmol) with constant stirring. The solution was refluxed on a water bath for 2-3 h and the solid residue obtained was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield = 50-70%.

Conclusion

On the basis of the analytical data, valence requirements, conductance, molecular weight, spectral, magnetic susceptibility measurements, it is proposed that **1** acts as a monobasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in **2-4** coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms. **2** (M = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu) is paramagnetic while, **2** (M = Zn, Cd), **3** and **4** are diamagnetic. The data suggest an octahedral structure for **2** and an eight-coordinate structure for **3** and **4**. The antimicrobial studies suggest that the coordination compounds **2-4** show significantly enhanced antimicrobial activity as compared to the free Schiff base (**1**). Owing to the broad spectrum nature of **2-4**, it is expected that the present coordination compounds may find use in pharmaceutical industry as antimicrobial agents for mankind, after testing its toxicity to human beings.

Acknowledgements

One of the authors (SC) is highly thankful to the authorities of National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra to provide an Institutional Fellowship to carry out the above work.

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